

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In reply refer to:
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U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
1455 Market Street,
San Francisco, California 95825

Subject: Formal Consultation for the Bay Point Restoration and Public Access Project, Suisun Marsh, Solano County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' File number 2017-00013)

Dear Dr. Bottoms:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) May 18, 2017, letter requesting formal consultation for the Bay Point Restoration and Public Access Project (project), City of Bay Point, Contra Costa County, California. The Corps determined that the proposed project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (SMHM). The Corps also determined that the proposed project may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) (CCR), the threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and its designated critical habitat, and the endangered soft bird's-beak (*Chloropyron molle* ssp. *molle*) and its critical habitat. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C 1531 *et seq.*)(Act).

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, "clapper-type" rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013; Chesser *et al.* 2014). However, the change does not change the current listing status of the species. The Service will continue to recognize the species as the California clapper rail until the change in common name and taxonomy of the California clapper rail to Ridgway's rail is officially entered into the Federal Register.

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' May 18, 2017, letter requesting consultation; (2) the May 2017 Biological Assessment for *the Bay Point Restoration and Public Access Project* (BA) prepared by ESA; and (3) other information available to the Service.

The Bay Point Regional Shoreline is within the designated critical habitat for the delta smelt and contains in some part all of the Primary Constituent Elements (PCEs). The project will be utilizing earth moving equipment (both on land and in the channel) and pile driving equipment in the aquatic environment that constitutes the delta smelt's designated critical habitat. The Service has reviewed the proposed project and its effects to the delta smelt's designated critical habitat. In designating critical habitat for the delta smelt, the Service identified the following PCEs essential to the conservation of the species:

PCE #1 is physical habitat for spawning. Spawning occurs primarily in the sloughs and shallow edges areas in the delta. Captive breeding has indicated sandy or gravel areas are preferred (Lindberg *et al.* 2003). The action area encompasses critical habitat that may be suitable for spawning and spawning activity is historically prevalent around the project area (California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) 2017). The project could disturb substrates that would increase turbidity; however, effects are considered temporary in nature and substrates are expected to return to pre-project conditions upon completion. The proposed actions are not expected to remove available spawning habitat substrates to a measurable degree. There is not expected to be a loss in habitat as the project site is targeted for restoration and would likely improve habitat conditions for the delta smelt.

PCE #2 is suitable water quality for all life stages. The project does not discharge effluent or reduce the dilution properties of the available water through diversion. There is no anticipated reduction in the quality of available water from any of the proposed actions.

PCE #3 is river flow. The proposed project is not expected to diminish river flow, since the project is not expected to reduce or alter the flows of the Sacramento River or the San Joaquin River.

PCE #4 is salinity for rearing. The proposed project is not expected to have any effect on salinity, since the river flows will not be affected, thus not affecting the position of X2.

Based on the above analysis, the Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the delta smelt's critical habitat.

Soft bird's-beak has potential to occur in the action area because the action area is within the current range of the species, salt marsh habitat is present and plants typically associated with soft bird's-beak occur within the action area such as pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*), and alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*). There are no previously documented occurrences of soft bird's-beak in the action area; however, the nearest extant occurrence is approximately 0.4 mile east (CDFW 2016; Occ. #7) and a second occurrence is located 1.2 mile to the west (CDFW 2016; Occ. #17). The applicant has proposed to conduct special-status plant surveys within 2 years prior to initiation of construction and any special status plants found will be recorded using a global positioning system unit and flagged for avoidance. Based on the proposals to survey and mark/protect any special status plants found, the Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the project will not likely adversely affect the soft bird's-beak. Critical habitat does not occur within the action area; therefore, none will be affected.

After review of the project description, listed species occurrence data, and habitats present within the action area, the Service has determined the actions proposed to occur through implementation of the proposed project are likely to adversely affect the SMHM, the CCR, and the delta smelt.

This document hereby represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the SMHM and the CCR. The Service has determined that the proposed project is suitable to append to the Service's December 4, 2004, *Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on Delta Smelt and its Critical Habitat* (Service File No. 1-1-04-F-0345) (Programmatic Biological Opinion) and that document represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects to the delta smelt from the proposed action.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The East Bay Regional Parks District (EBRPD) proposes to restore tidal wetland habitat, improve a public-use trail which includes the construction of a steel truss walk bridge and improve the public use kayak and hand launched vessel access which includes a new gangway and floating dock within the Bay Point Regional Shoreline. Earthwork will generally occur between May and December. Work is anticipated to occur in phases, each phase taking place during one construction season. Equipment anticipated for construction includes excavators, dozers, dump trucks, scrapers, pile drivers, concrete mixers, water trucks, crane, pumps, rollers, and sheepsfoot compactors. Construction of the kayak launch will additionally require a barge mounted vibratory pile driver. Dewatering may be required. The EBPRD also proposes to conduct ongoing vegetation control in the form of grazing, weeding, and mowing along with qualitative and quantitative restoration monitoring post construction which includes watering and invasive species control. Construction access to the site is provided from Highway 4 via Willow Pass Road, Port Chicago Highway and McAvoy Road. Barge access can be provided from Suisun Bay through the "J" channel.

Habitat Restoration

The project restores and enhances approximately 16 acres of tidal marsh and channel, 1.6 acres of tidal panne, 0.3 acre of seasonal wetland, and 10.1 acres of coastal grassland and coastal scrub. High areas will be lowered to tidal marsh elevations and reconnected to the tides of the Suisun Bay. Excavated materials will be used to build gently sloped transitions from tidal into upland habitat. Following site grading, lower elevation areas will be ceded to natural vegetation recruitment while higher areas will be re-vegetated with native plants and maintained as needed to ensure establishment. Part of the remnant berm that extends east of the restoration area will be lowered to tidal marsh elevations to eliminate it as a predatory access route into the marshplain and bank of the existing "J" channel. For further details of the specific restoration plan, please refer to the "2.2.1 Habitat Restoration" section of the BA.

Public Access

Harrier Trail

The Harrier Trail is currently a multi-use trail on an unimproved perimeter service road. The project will upgrade the road to meet current accessibility standards for park visitors and provide all weather access for maintenance and emergency vehicles. Improvements to the Harrier Trail will be made in two sections. The first section extends from the EBRPD parking area along the

southern and western perimeter of the site to a turnaround area at the northwest corner of the site. This section will be built for full size vehicles and includes increasing the elevation to 15 feet North American Vertical Datum of 1988 (NAVD88), resurfacing with American Disabilities ACT (ADA) compliant grades, and the construction of a 60-foot diameter pad to accommodate a paved turnaround radius of 25 feet with a 5-foot perimeter buffer for lookout signage and benches. The second section extends from the northeast turnaround to complete the loop. This section is designed for lighter services vehicles (all-terrain vehicles) and includes increasing the elevation to 13.5 feet NAVD88 and resurfacing with ADA compliant grades.

Channel Crossing

A channel crossing structure will be constructed where the Harrier Trail crosses the proposed tidal channel connecting the restored marsh to the "J" Channel. The crossing will be a 46-foot long, 12.5-foot wide, prefabricated steel truss bridge. The bridge will be placed on two abutments at either end of the bridge. The abutments will be located at the marsh plain level and four piles would secure each abutment into the ground. A 6-inch concrete deck will be placed at the base of the deck and will be flush with the adjacent gravel Harrier Trail. Trail railings will be placed on both sides of the bridge.

Fencing, Buffers, and Signs

A 4-foot high fencing with a gap for wildlife passage and gates for maintenance access is proposed along the Harrier Trail to restrict access to habitat areas. Signs will be posted at regular intervals along the fence alerting visitors of the sensitivity of adjacent habitat areas. Interpretive panels and benches for lookouts will be installed along the Harrier Trail.

Kayak and Hand Launched Vessel Access

Kayak and hand launched vessel access to the "J" channel will be improved by construction of a kayak launch. The structure will consist of an 80-foot long, 3-foot wide gangway extending from the existing spur trail on the neighboring McAvoy Marina property onto a low-freeboard floating dock in the "J" channel. The gangway would be secured to land by a foundation at the spur trail. The floating dock would be held in place by up to three 1-foot-diameter piles.

Spur of the Great California Delta Trail

A new 500-foot long trail segment would be installed to connect the existing parking lot to the existing spur trail. The 10-foot wide trail would be comprised of 6 inches of compacted base rock placed over a layer of filter fabric. The trail would be excavated or filled as needed to meet grade and exposed edges of the fill material would be seeded similar to upland areas similar to the Harrier Trail. Approximately 950 feet of existing spur trail located north of the new trail connection would be widened and rehabilitated. A 10-foot wide and 1,350-foot long aluminum boardwalk with railings would be constructed above the existing spur trail north of the trail rehabilitation segment. The base of the boardwalk would be positioned at least 4 feet above the ground surface and would be supported by 195 helical piles drilled approximately 45 feet below the boardwalk. Earthen ramps would connect the trail rehabilitation segment to the boardwalk and connect the boardwalk to the trail's north terminus. The two ramps would be approximately 85 feet long and would be seeded similar to the upland areas along the Harrier Trail.

Conservation Measures

General

- A Service-approved biologist will provide training to field management and construction personnel on the importance of protecting environmental resources. Communication efforts and training will take place during preconstruction meetings so that construction personnel are aware of their responsibilities and the importance of compliance. Construction personnel will be educated in the types of sensitive resources located in the action area and the measures required to avoid impacts on these resources. Materials covered in the training program will include environmental rules and regulations of the specific project and requirements for limiting activities to the construction right-of-way and avoiding demarcated sensitive resource areas. Training seminars will educate construction supervisors and managers on the need for resource avoidance and protection, roles and responsibilities, and conservation measures. If new construction personnel are added to the project the contractor will ensure the new personnel receive the mandatory training before starting work.
- A representative will be appointed during the employee education program to be the contact for any employee or contractor that may inadvertently kill or injure a listed species or find a dead, injured, or entrapped individual. The representative's name will be provided to the Service before initiation of ground disturbance.
- A Service-approved biologist will conduct pre-construction surveys. If a listed species is discovered, construction activities will not begin in the immediate vicinity of the individual until the Service and/or the CDFW is contacted and the individual has been allowed to leave the construction area. The individual will be allowed to leave of its own volition without coercion or harassment. Any special-status species observed during surveys will be reported to the Service and CDFW so the observations can be added to the California Natural Diversity Database.
- Vegetation removal will be conducted with a Service-approved biologist present. The Service-approved biologist will be able to temporarily stop work if a listed species is present.
- A Stormwater Pollution Prevention Plan and a Hazardous Material Management Plan (HMMP) will be in place prior to construction. The project proponents and/or their contractors will develop and implement spill prevention and control measures to minimize the effects of spills of hazardous, toxic, or petroleum substances during construction. The HMMP will incorporate measures for the proper containment and storage of hazardous materials. In the event of a contaminant spill, the work at the site will immediately cease until the contractor has contained and mitigated the spill. The contractor will immediately prevent further contamination, notify the appropriate authorities, and mitigate damage as appropriate.

California Clapper Rail and Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

- Silt fencing will be installed between suitable SMHM habitat and active work areas to exclude SMHM from entering work areas prior to grading or heavy equipment operation.
- Work will be scheduled to avoid extreme high tides when there is potential for SMHM to move to higher, drier grounds. All equipment will be staged on existing roadways away from the project site when not in use. Extreme high tides would be in excess of seven feet as predicted for the nearest tide gauge, Port Chicago tide gauge.
- Activities within 700 feet, including vegetation removal, will be avoided during the breeding season from February through August 31. If areas within or adjacent to CCR habitat cannot be avoided during the breeding season, protocol level surveys shall be conducted to determine CCR locations. If no CCR territories are detected or their territories can be avoided, then the project activities may proceed at that location. If nesting CCRs are determined to be present, activities will not occur within 700 feet of an identified calling center, unless the intervening distance across a major slough channel or across a substantial barrier between the CCR calling center and any project activity is greater than 200 feet, then it may proceed at that location within the breeding season.

Delta Smelt

- In-water construction activities, including tidal channel excavation would occur during the in-water work window of August 1 through November 30.
- A silt curtain will be installed during breaching and tidal channel excavation to prevent the sedimentation or other construction related impacts on the surrounding waters.
- Underwater sound monitoring will be performed during pile-driving activities. A qualified biologist/natural resource specialist will be present during such work to monitor construction activities and compliance within the terms and conditions of the permits.
- Piles will be driven by vibratory or non-impact methods that result in sound pressures below threshold levels established by the National Marine Fisheries Service to the extent feasible. The use of cushion blocks, air bubble diffusers or other sound attenuating controls may be required if underwater sound monitoring indicates that sound levels exceed threshold levels.

Action Area

The action area is defined as all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action (50 CFR 402.02). The action area for this section 7 consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the construction zone, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, or movement associated with the proposed project. The action area includes the project footprint and staging and access areas. After review of the BA and the project description, the Service determines that the action area includes the Bay Point Regional Shoreline, the "J" channel, and the portions of the Harrier Trail

and Great California Delta Trail. The action area totals approximately 180 acres and encompasses the approximate 52-acre construction footprint, the staging areas, and a 700-foot buffer for noise disturbance in the salt marsh. This distance was determined by the Service based on telemetry studies (Albertson 1995) that estimated the average area of a CCR home range equivalent to a circle with a 450-foot radius; the Service then added a 250-foot buffer zone to that distance to ensure avoidance, to arrive at 700 feet.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. "Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the Status of the Species, which describes the rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the Environmental Baseline, which analyzes the condition of the species in the action area, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the Effects of the Action, which determines the direct and indirect impacts of the proposed Federal action and the effects of any interrelated or interdependent activities on the species; and (4) the Cumulative Effects, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the action area on the species.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

The status of California clapper rail and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at:

https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf.

Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. The status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Delta Smelt

The status of the species has been updated since the issuance of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Please refer to page 6 of the 2010 delta smelt 5 year review and page 87264 of the 2016 Candidate Notice of Review for the status of the species. Electronic copies of these documents are available at http://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc3570.pdf and <http://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/FR-2013-11-22/pdf/2013-27391.pdf>.

Currently, the spawning stock of delta smelt appears to be at its second lowest abundance on record, the lowest having been recorded during Water Year 2016 (Table 1). The 2017 Fall Midwater Trawl (FMWT) Index was 8, the second lowest value on record. The CDFW Spring Kodiak Trawl (SKT) monitors the adult spawning stock of delta smelt and serves as an indication for the relative number and distribution of spawners in the system. The Service has calculated an absolute abundance estimate for adult spawners in water year 2017 using January and February SKT data. This absolute abundance estimate¹ is also the second lowest on record (Table 1). The population size of adult delta smelt January-February (2017) was estimated to be between 22,000 and 92,000 fish with a point estimate of 47,786. The January-February (2016) point estimates were the lowest values since 2002 and suggested delta smelt experienced increased mortality during extreme drought conditions occurring during 2013-2015. While 2017 estimates likely represent an increase in recruitment and survival from the prior year, the continued low parental stock of delta smelt relative to historical numbers suggest the population will continue to be vulnerable to stochastic events and operational changes that may occur in response until successive years of increased population growth result in a substantial increase of abundance.

Table 1.

Three indicators of adult delta smelt status for water years 2002-2017. Column 2 is the CDFW Fall Midwater Trawl Index by water year (i.e., the indices for calendar years 2001-2017). Column 3 is the CDFW Spring Kodiak Trawl Index. Column 4 is an estimate of adult delta smelt abundance during January and February that the Service calculates from the Spring Kodiak Trawl Survey.

<u>Water Year</u>	<u>FMWT Index (unitless)</u>	<u>SKT Index (unitless)</u>	<u>Jan-Feb SKT abundance estimate (thousands of fish)</u>
2002	603	N/A	739.8
2003	139	N/A	634
2004	210	99.7	654.5
2005	74	52.9	477.8
2006	26	18.2	186.8
2007	41	32.5	292
2008	28	24.1	325.3
2009	23	43.8	365.9
2010	17	27.4	169.4
2011	29	18.8	290.8

¹ The Service completed a new adult delta smelt abundance estimation procedure based on CDFW's SKT data for January and February (see Table 1). This procedure has recently been updated from that used in 2016. While these estimates likely represent a minimum population size due to the method's reliance on survey data, this is our current best estimate of population size.

2012	343	130.2	772.3
2013	42	20.4	212.5
2014	18	30.1	207.6
2015	9	13.8	139.3
2016	7	1.8	16.2
2017	8	3.8	47.8

Environmental Baseline

The proposed project is located on the southern edge of Suisun Bay along the northern shoreline of Contra Costa County and is predominantly tidal marsh habitat with a large man-made channel and constructed levee. The site is bordered by a small marina to the east and experiences moderate human activity for recreational use.

Small mammal trapping in the summer of 2016 resulted in the positive identification of four SMHM on site and historical occurrences of SMHM have been documented within 1 mile east and west of the action area (CDFW 2017). Suitable habitat is present and SMHM could potentially occur in the action area.

California clapper rail occurs sporadically and in low numbers at various locations throughout the Suisun Marsh area. They have been found recurrently since 1978 in shoreline marshes from Martinez east to Port Chicago, Suisun and Hill sloughs, and the western reaches of Cutoff Slough (Herzog *et al.* 2005; Service 2013). Although there are currently no records of CCR within the action area, protocol level surveys have not been conducted within the action area. The closest occurrence is approximately 1.5 miles to the west and suitable habitat is present; therefore, CCR could potentially occur in the action area.

Precipitation in Water Year 2017 was recorded as the wettest on record in the Sacramento Valley Basin and resulting high outflows from the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta have provided spawning opportunities towards the San Pablo Bay, as evidenced by data collected by CDFW and the Service during regular fish monitoring surveys. Delta smelt have been recorded in the Carquinez Strait, east San Pablo Bay, and the lower Napa River. As a result, the progeny of this year's spawning stock may occur in the vicinity of the project area where they will rear until the subsequent winter migration. This is especially likely if the low-salinity zone remains near Carquinez Strait. Bay Point Shoreline is tidally influenced and connects to the Suisun Bay. Delta smelt are known to occur within the waterways of the Suisun Bay and associated marsh complexes and could provide suitable habitat for delta smelt during this current water year and similar water years in the future.

Effects of the Proposed Project

California Clapper Rail

Noise, vibrations, and visual disturbance from construction activities and heavy equipment may result in the harassment of individual CCR in the adjacent habitat and expose them to predation if they were flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. Noise or other construction disturbance during the CCR breeding season (February 1-August 31) could result in

the loss of breeding activity or nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. To minimize adverse effects to breeding, work is planned to occur September 1 – January 31 which is outside of the nesting season. The applicant has proposed that work could extend into the breeding season if construction is not completed within the aforementioned work window. If work extends into the breeding season for the CCR, the applicant has proposed to conduct protocol-level surveys to locate nesting CCR and establish buffer zones. The protocol-level surveys may also result in harassment of the CCR through the broadcast of CCR vocalizations to detect the species. Restoration of marsh habitats will result in the increase of 3.8 acres of tidal wetland which may have future benefit for the CCR.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The proposed project could cause displacement of SMHM if individuals were compelled to move away from construction and demolition activities to avoid being disturbed. Displaced individuals could be exposed to increased risk from predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success through abandonment of a nesting area, failure to breed, or abandonment or failure of a litter. Potential displacement of SMHM individuals would be minimized through the use of preconstruction surveys and monitoring by a Service-approved biologist during hand removal of vegetation and installation of exclusion fencing. Wetlands in the action area could become contaminated during construction if fuel or other hazardous materials were to spill into the channel or adjacent wetlands. Contamination of wetlands or waters would be minimized by implementing a spill prevention plan, BMPs, and a storm water pollution prevention plan. Vegetation removal and grading activities will result in temporary loss of habitat. Temporary impacts would amount to approximately 1.04 acre of northern coastal salt marsh habitat; however, restoration of marsh habitats will result in the increase of 3.8 acres of tidal wetland which will likely have future benefit for the SMHM.

Delta Smelt

The applicant has proposed to conduct work within the recommended work window of August 1 through November 30 and additional proposed conservation measures which are consistent with the guidelines of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The proposed project is not expected to result in any additional effects not already analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. The Service is not aware of specific projects that might affect the CCR, SMHM or delta smelt in the action area that are currently under review by State, county, or local authorities.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the CCR, SMHM, delta smelt, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed action, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CCR, SMHM or delta smelt. This is based on the small size of the

affected suitable habitat area, the fact that habitat disturbance will be temporary and short-term, and the implementation of conservation measures.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicants to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual CCR, SMHM and delta smelt will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of CCR, SMHM and delta smelt that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. Harassment of all CCR and SMHM within suitable habitat of the action area (approximately 180 acres and encompasses the entire 52-acre construction footprint, staging areas, and a 700-foot buffer for noise disturbance in the salt marsh).
2. Harassment of all delta smelt within suitable aquatic habitat of the action area (approximately 9 acres within the "J" channel and 1,000-foot noise disturbance into the Suisun Bay).

Upon implementation of the reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determines that the levels of take are not likely to result in jeopardy to the CCR, SMHM or the delta smelt.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measures are necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the CCR, SMHM and the delta smelt:

1. The Corps will minimize the potential for harassment of CCR, SMHM and delta smelt.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure that the applicants comply with the following terms and conditions, which implement their respective reasonable and prudent measures described above. These terms and conditions are non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harassment of the CCR, SMHM and delta smelt from project related activities by implementation of the Conservation Measures as described in the Description of the Proposed Action in this biological opinion or as modified by the Terms and Conditions of this document.
 - b. The Corps shall ensure that the applicants immediately notify the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped CCR, SMHM, or delta smelt, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-5603.
 - c. The Corps shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
 - d. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this project.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1b, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
3. The applicants shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within sixty (60) calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the CCR, SMHM, and delta smelt if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-5603; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in re-vegetation efforts.

2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
3. Assist the Service in implementing other recovery actions identified within most current recovery plans for the CCR, SMHM and delta smelt.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the Bay Point Restoration and Public Access Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat not considered in this opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any additional take will not be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, pending reinitiation.

If you have any questions regarding this response to the Bay Point Restoration and Public Access Project, please contact Brian Hansen, Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or by telephone at (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Coordinator, via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 08FBDT00-2017-F-0199 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

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